

Water droplet erosion response of 316L steel manufactured conventionally and additively using selective laser melting

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Abstract

The technological manufacturing history of a material is one of the essential factors that affect its microstructure and related mechanical properties. This fact becomes even more significant when replacing the conventional material with another variant, prepared, e.g., using a method of additive manufacturing (AM), such as selective laser melting (SLM), is required. As the specific hierarchical microstructure inherent to the SLM process may potentially alter the resistance of a material against liquid droplet erosion, the comparative experimental tests using an ultrasonic water jet generator were performed on several variants of AISI 316L stainless steel, namely conventional wrought material with typical polyhedral grains and material produced using SLM with characteristic microstructure including melt pools, columnar grains, and solidification/dislocation cells. In addition to the as-built SLM microstructure, two other modifications were obtained using a heat treatment under different annealing temperatures. Flat surfaces, both parallel and perpendicular to the building direction for all microstructure variants, were subjected to water droplet erosion induced by an ultrasonically excited pulsating water jet (PWJ), and a possible effect of microstructure anisotropy of SLM 316L steel on the erosion damage was assessed. Different time exposures were employed to cover all erosion stages from the incubation period to material removal, and the response of all material variants to PWJ was related to their characteristic microstructures with an emphasis on erosion mechanisms. SLM microstructure exhibited prolongation of the incubation period and higher resistance in erosion wear in comparison with its conventional counterpart. The orientation of the build direction affected the response of the SLM material to water jet impingement.

Keywords

Additive manufacturing (AM), selective laser melting (SLM), 316L steel, pulsating water jet (PWJ), erosion evolution, scanning electron microscopy (SEM), transmission electron microscopy (TEM).

Highlights

- SLM material showed higher resistance to PWJ water impingement than wrought samples.
- Building direction affected erosion resistance of SLM samples.
- Post-heat treatment resulted in variability in erosion intensity for SLM samples.
- SLM microstructure complexity affected the material's response to PWJ water impingement.

1. Introduction

Erosion due to the liquid droplet impingement on rigid flat surfaces occurs in natural and technological conditions. Despite the appreciable effort devoted to different aspects of this topic, the mechanisms of droplet erosion have yet to be satisfactorily explained. Water droplet interaction is defined by the kinematic and thermodynamic properties of a droplet and the properties of a material, such as hardness, yield stress, elasticity, plasticity, and surface topography. Currently, the topic of erosion resistance of materials against repeatedly acting loading forces in the form of impinging drops resonates in various industries [1]. This feature is decisive, for instance, in critical infrastructures such as pipelines in nuclear power plants or the erosion of the last stage of steam turbine blades [2]. It has been found that the magnitude of impact pressure (known as the hammer effect) capable of overcoming the yield strength of ductile materials is characterized by the impact velocity of the droplet with volumetric mass density [3]. The propagation velocity of the acoustic wave toward the droplet from the contact periphery also characterizes this impact pressure [4], which lasts some microseconds, followed by lateral outflow [5].

The mechanical properties of the material, its composition, microstructure, and grain size play an essential role in the development of erosion damage with respect to time, i.e., the erosion phases. Generally, the classification of erosion evolution due to liquid droplet impingement can be broadly divided into initial and advanced stages [6], each of them is characterized by distinct mechanisms and effects on the material surface. The initial stages involve surface roughening and gradual elastic and plastic deformation at the grain level. During this phase, asymmetric gradients in the strengthened regions are formed locally, creating high-energy fields. With further action of water droplets, the deformation capacity of the grains is exhausted, leading to failure at their boundaries. From the perspective of classical mechanics, this marks the end of the so-called incubation phase [7] and the beginning of the advanced erosion stage [8], which is related mainly to structural damage and material loss. As the frequency of cracks increases, the deformation continues to reach limit states, which indicates the impending release of artifacts from the parent material [9]. After reaching the maximum erosion, the velocity of the released material begins to decrease due to the roughened surface, which acts as a protective barrier. The sharp edges [10] of the surface disrupt the structural integrity of the water drop's surface envelope, eliminating the hammer effect. In the final stages, erosion may be caused by lateral flow, leading to the possible formation of subsurface microchannels [11].

Numerous technical devices have been developed to test various erosion parameters [12]. However, the main drawback of all these methods for more systematic fundamental studies is the stochastic distribution of water droplets per unit area of different coupons. The pulsating water jet (PWJ) technique described in [13] allows for the concentration of water droplets at a specific epicenter of the collision. This method, based on the ultrasonically excited pulses in a water jet, is used to investigate the erosion stages of metallic materials and/or to modify the surface properties using the interaction of water clusters with the surface. A great effort has been devoted to predicting the various stages of erosion due to the concentrated action of water droplets when the PWJ technique brings the possibility of more precise timing of droplet impacts [14], [15], [16]. Slot et al. [7] focused on erosion prediction using experimental fatigue-based data for AISI 316L, including factors such as subsurface hardening and compressive stresses. A recent study by Poloprudský et al. [16] focused on the analysis of the initial stages of erosion via the kernel average misorientation (KAM) mapping using electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD), where a real evolution in grain orientation and misorientation angles within the grains due to water droplet impingement was recorded. The tilting of the surface layer of grains was identified as an essential incubation erosion mechanism.

Current advances in technological procedures allow components or parts to be produced by additive manufacturing. The most important contribution is the production of near-net-shaped parts and the fabrication of complex geometries that cannot be made by conventional processes. Among these methods, selective laser melting (SLM) represents the most common and frequently utilized technology for various metallic materials [17]. Due to the different microstructures inherent to the specific complex nature of so-called micro-welding technology, the SLM materials show significantly different properties from those of conventional counterparts [18]. Austenitic stainless steel AISI 316L is one of the most well-known types of stainless steel. It is frequently used in various industrial applications due to its high mechanical properties, corrosion and oxidation resistance, high-temperature strength, and excellent weldability [19]. The last-mentioned feature is advantageously used in SLM technology, which adopts a laser as an energy source for selective fusion of a metallic powder bed in a layer-by-layer process to build three-dimensional (3D) parts [20]. Due to very high-temperature gradients and solidification rates together with repeated cooling/heating cycles, a unique hierarchical microstructure [21], with columnar grains including cellular dislocation sub-grains and nano-oxides [22] is created, which is entirely different from its wrought counterpart with typical polyhedral grains and annealing twins [14]. When the low porosity of SLM parts is assured, it provides the material with a considerably higher yield stress, higher ultimate tensile strength and hardness, and slightly lower ductility compared to the conventional variant [23]. In addition to possible porosity, other specific features inherent to SLM technology must be considered, such as microstructural and mechanical anisotropy and high residual stresses [24], [25]. The main factor hindering a broader utilization of SLM materials in real applications is the limited knowledge of the relationship between complex, unique microstructures of materials and their performance under specific loading conditions.

The primary objective of this work is to fill a critical research gap in understanding the erosion behavior of additively manufactured metals under PWJ treatment. The pulsating water jet technique, providing the varying impacts of water droplets over time, was used to study the response of modified microstructures of 316L steel due to SLM, the different orientation (build direction), and heat treatments to erosion. The findings could have significant implications for developing more durable materials and optimizing manufacturing processes in various industrial applications. The microstructure and mechanical properties, including hardness, of SLM 316L steel can be significantly altered by various post-heat treatments; therefore, two heat treatment types, stress relieving (850°C for 1 hour), and solution annealing (1150°C for 2 hours), were included to identify the optimal properties for maximum erosion resistance.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Samples production

Gas-atomized 316L stainless steel powder supplied by Renishaw, with a spherical morphology and particle size range of 15–45 μm , was used for the SLM production of samples (SLMed). The chemical composition of the powder is listed in **Table 1**. As a counterpart to SLMed samples, the conventional wrought polycrystalline 316L steel was used (see **Table 1**) in the as-received state (**AR**). Samples were cut from a 20 mm thick hot rolled plate in a solution annealed state [14], perpendicularly to the rolling plane.

Selective laser melting of 316L steel was performed at VSB-TUO Ostrava using a Renishaw AM400 3D printer equipped with the ytterbium fiber pulsed laser with a maximum nominal power of 400 W and a focus diameter of 70 μm . Rectangular blocks with dimensions of 25 × 100 × 5 mm were printed under a protective argon atmosphere without preheating the building platform. Two orientations of samples were used: samples labeled **TD** were printed vertically with a meander scanning strategy, and samples

labeled **BD** were printed horizontally with a chessboard scanning strategy. The layer thickness was 50 μm . For borders/contouring of samples, the conditions were set as: power 110 W, point distance 20 μm , and exposure time 100 μs . For hatches, the conditions were as follows: power 200 W, point distance 60 μm , exposure time 80 μs . The adoption of SLM process parameters stated above resulted in a relative density of 99.1%, as revealed by Archimedes' method in acetone using a Sartorius Quintix 224-1S precision balance equipped with a density determination kit for samples printed both in horizontal and vertical orientation (**BD** and **TD** samples).

Material state directly after additive manufacturing without any further post-heat treatment, i.e. as-built state, is labeled **AB**. Selected SLMed samples were subjected to two post-processing heat treatments: stress relieving at 850 $^{\circ}\text{C}/1\text{h}$, labeled **SR**, and solution annealing at 1150 $^{\circ}\text{C}/2\text{h}$, labeled **SA**.

Table 1 The chemical composition of SLM and conventional 316L steels

Element (wt.%)	Cr	Ni	Mo	C	Si	Mn	P	S	N	O	Fe
Virgin powder for SLM [26]	18.3	11.2	2.2	0.02	1.1	1.9	-	0.004	0.03	0.05	Bal.
Conventional steel [14]	16.6	10.0	2.0	0.02	0.4	1.2	0.032	0.001	0.04	-	Bal.

As apparent from **Table 2**, the experimental material base contains seven different material states, i.e., six different SLM states created by the combination of SLM processing and post-processing parameters and one conventionally produced wrought material as the reference sample.

Table 2 Various states of experimental materials AISI 316 L

Technology	Orientation	Microstructure state (heat treatment conditions) *		
SLM	TD sample	AB : as-built	SR : 850 $^{\circ}\text{C}/1\text{h}$	SA : 1150 $^{\circ}\text{C}/2\text{h}$
SLM	BD sample	AB : as-built	SR : 850 $^{\circ}\text{C}/1\text{h}$	SA : 1150 $^{\circ}\text{C}/2\text{h}$
Conventional	-	AR : as received	—	—

*Both stress relieving (**SR**) and solution annealing (**SA**) post-heat treatments were followed by air cooling.

2.2. Methodology

Various techniques were adopted to reveal the microstructure and erosion stages of individual material states under investigation. The metallographic preparation consisted of mechanical grinding, chemical mechanical polishing using colloidal silica, and, in the case of selected regions of interest, etching using a modified Beraha's reagent (distilled water, hydrochloric acid, ammonium bifluoride, potassium metabisulfite) after electro-polishing was applied. A digital optical microscope (OM, Olympus DSX1000) and a scanning electron microscope (SEM, Tescan LYRA 3 XMU FEG/SEMx/FIB) equipped with an EBSD detector (Oxford Instruments, Aztec control system) were used for microstructure observation and evaluation of mechanisms of erosion in various stages of surface degradation. The EBSD technique was adopted to characterize microstructure, grain morphology, and crystallographic texture. High-resolution characterization of the dislocation arrangements and possible presence of nano-oxide particles was performed using transmission electron microscopy (TEM, JEOL JEM-2100F, and Thermo Fisher Scientific Talos F200i) operating at 200 kV and equipped with an energy-dispersive spectrometer (EDS, Oxford Instruments X-MAX 80). The scanning mode (STEM) for imaging and selected area electron diffraction (SAED) for particle analysis were adopted. Thin TEM foils were prepared both conventionally (by electrolytic thinning at 12 $^{\circ}\text{C}/70\text{ V}$ using a 5 wt.% solution of perchloric acid in acetic acid) and using the focused ion beam (FIB) technique in SEM.

The surfaces of samples exposed to PWJ were analyzed using a non-contact approach, employing an InfiniteFocus G5 optical 3D measurement system (Bruker, Alicona). This instrument utilizes the focus-variation technology combined with vertical scanning to measure surfaces with varying slopes, depths, and dimensions, achieving vertical resolution at the nanometer scale and lateral resolution in the micrometer range. The surface data from the PWJ-treated samples were then evaluated for the maximum depth and volume of the erosion crater based on the selected technological conditions. The scanned surface data obtained from the microscope were assessed using MountainsSPIP software. The erosion region was identified, and the maximum depth of the erosion and the total eroded volume were evaluated. Five erosion craters were generated for each testing parameter, and each was evaluated separately. The mean and standard deviation values of the depth and volume removed were used to determine the erosion trends, obtained by all five measured values for each tested parameter, to have statistical significance. Vickers hardness (HV1) measurements were conducted using a DuraScan 70 G5 ZwickRoell with a load force of 1 kg and a hold time of 10 s for all material states. At least 10 measurements were performed for each sample.

2.3. Material microstructure

The microstructure of experimental materials before PWJ experiments was evaluated using the techniques described above. The results of the SEM and EBSD investigations are presented in **Figure 1**. The shape, size, and crystallography of gas-atomized 316L powder used for SLM printing are shown in **Figure 1a**. Polyhedral grains with annealing twins were observed for a conventional wrought material variant (see **Figure 1b**). The microstructure of 316L SLM samples in the **AB** state (highlighted by modified Beraha's reagent) with a typical melt pool pattern recognizable at small magnification is apparent from **Figure 1c**. Higher magnification depicts the unique hierarchical microstructure of SLM 316L steel in the **AB** state, namely the SLM-process-induced cellular solidification/dislocation substructure, the size of which is typically in the range of 500–800 nm [21].

EBSD maps in IPF coloring, without band contrast but with enhanced grain boundaries in the same magnification for all three material states of SLMed samples, are presented in **Figure 2** and compared to the conventional sample. The preferential orientation of grains in the microstructure of SLM samples was evaluated and compared to the conventional sample. In the case of side view analysis, the results of the obtained texture are shown in **Figure 2**. **AR** and **SR** samples exhibit a mild texture in $\langle 101 \rangle$ crystallographic direction in the IPF Y pole figure corresponding to a MUD value (multiple of uniform density) of approximately 2 (see **Figure 2d**). **SR** heat treatment was performed to remove internal residual stress. It resulted only in the partial rearrangement of dislocation cells without any change in the shape and orientation of grains. **SA** resulted in a complete recrystallization and significant removal of texture (MUD value in $\langle 101 \rangle$ crystallographic direction is 1.4).

Vickers hardness was evaluated for all material states, and the results are listed in **Table 3**. The highest hardness was achieved for SLM 316L steel in the **AB** state. The **SR** treatment accomplished only a minor decrease in hardness, while **SA** led to a decrease in hardness, reaching around 10 % compared to the **AB** state.

Figure 1 SEM micrographs of 316L steel, the microstructure, and corresponding EBSD maps in IPF coloring: a) atomized powder, b) conventional AR state, and c) SLMed sample in AB state (side view, SLM build direction is upwards).

Table 3 Vickers hardness of 316L steels produced conventionally and additively.

Technology	Conventional	SLM		
Heat treatment	AR: As received (hot rolled)	AB: As built	SR: 850°C/1h	SA: 1150°C/2h
Hardness on TD samples	186±5 HV1	219±6 HV1	215±7 HV1	199±6 HV1
Hardness on BD samples		235±7 HV1	234±8 HV1	205±8 HV1

Figure 2 The microstructure of different material states of SLM 316L samples as revealed on the side surface using EBSD maps in IPF coloring for different material states together with IPF Y figures describing crystallographic texture for a), b) AB state, c), d) SR state, and e), f) SA state. (SLM build direction is upwards.)

Documentation of the finest details of characteristic hierarchical SLM microstructure is possible only by adopting the TEM technique. Typical examples of dislocation structures (overviews and details) for all three microstructural states (**AB**, **SR**, and **SA**) of SLMed 316L steel are presented in **Figure 3**. The **AB** state is typical of cells, where walls consist of a high density of tangled dislocations (see **Figure 3a**). **SR** partially affected the cellular dislocation microstructure induced by SLM. The cells are still visible, but dislocation density has decreased considerably, with almost single dislocations being visible within cell walls, as seen in the inset in **Figure 3b**. **SA** was intended to recrystallize the microstructure and restore the plasticity of the sample. It resulted in a complete dissolution of the fine cellular substructure, leading to a significant decrease in dislocation density into a microstructure resembling a conventional state, and, thus, to an irreversible reduction in the yield stress of the material.

Figure 3 Bright field STEM micrographs of dislocation substructure in different states of SLM 316L steel: a) **AB**, b) **SR**, and c) **SA** state.

Contrary to conventional 316L steel, materials prepared by the SLM technique contain a certain amount of fine globular oxide nanoparticles in the microstructure. These particles have been evidenced using EDS/STEM mapping for all three microstructure states of the SLM 316L steel (see **Figure 4**). Numerous very fine globular oxides, rich mainly in silicon and manganese, can be seen within cellular walls for **AB** and **SR** states (see **Figure 4a** and **Figure 4b**). While the **SR** had no visible effect on the size and distribution of Si-Mn type oxide nanoparticles, considerable changes in both the distribution and size of oxide particles are apparent for the high-temperature **SA** state. Due to a complete dissolution of cellular substructure, considerably larger oxide particles are situated mainly at or close to the boundaries of the fully recrystallized microstructure (see **Figure 4c**).

Figure 4 Bright-field STEM micrographs and EDS/STEM elemental maps showing oxide particles in different states of SLM 316L steel: a) **AB**, b) **SR**, and c) **SA** state.

Another characteristic of SLM 316L steel in the **AB** state is the presence of micro-segregation accompanying solidification during very high cooling rates, which has been repeatedly reported in the literature (see, e.g., [27], [28]). The enrichment of cell boundaries in Cr and Mo and their depletion in

Fe is apparent in **Figure 4a**. After the application of the post-heat treatments, no chemical micro-segregation could be detected.

2.4. PWJ experimental setup and conditions

The experimental setup of the experiments is described in **Figure 5**. The PWJ method generated water droplets directed at a specific surface area of the target material, causing loading by repeated impact pressure for a time period. The principle of droplet erosion generation and time loading reduction is as follows: water pressure is generated by a high-pressure Hammelman HDP 253 pump and delivered through a pipeline into the chamber in which the sonotrode oscillates [13]. The oscillations are driven via piezoceramics by the ultrasonic acoustic generator ECOSON WJ-UG-630-40. The experimental conditions of PWJ impingement listed in **Table 4** involve technological and erosion parameters. A liquid at supply pressure p passes through a nozzle with diameter d , transforming into a high-speed water jet with flow rate Q at subsonic speed v_w . According to [29], the acoustic chamber length l_c can be adjusted to achieve optimal erosion parameters.

Table 4 Experimental conditions

Technological conditions of hydraulic system						Erosion conditions		
p	d	Q	v_w	l_c	z	E_t	f_s	V_i
[MPa]	[mm]	[l/min]	[m/s]	[mm]	[mm]	[s]	[kHz]	[mm ³]
50	0.6	4.83	285	10	62	1;2;3;4;5;6;7;8;9;10	40	2.01

The fluctuating water pressure in the acoustic chamber is gradually shaped into wavering axial flow velocities (**Figure 5 b**), leading to the breakup of the continuous stream into clusters of water droplets that impinge on the target material's surface. The breakdown of the water stream into water clusters is created gradually, depending on the increasing distance from the nozzle outlet, the so-called standoff distance. The stair trajectory procedure [30] was applied to determine the optimal standoff distance z . The evaluation criterion was to determine the distance range at which the water flow is divided into complete monodisperse water clusters. The clusters of water droplets load the material with the biggest possible erosion potential at a given water volume and velocity. Material erosion occurs during the interaction of droplets hitting the surface with a nominal frequency f_s . According to the applied $p = 50$ MPa and $d = 0.6$ mm at a $f_s = 40$ kHz, the target material is loaded by the impact of water clusters in an incident volume of $V_i = 2.01$ mm³. The exposure time E_t was set incrementally. It provides a range of erosive loads on the target material, causing erosion from the initial surface roughening to material removal. Each sample underwent five repetitions of PWJ treatment to ensure reproducibility and measure deviations in erosive effect in dependence on the microstructure variation related to the combination of processing and post-processing parameters.

Figure 5 Experimental setup: a) principle of PWJ method, b) break up of water stream into clusters and optimal standoff distance, and PWJ treatment concerning the directionality of material microstructure for c) SLMed TD samples, d) SLMed BD samples, and e) reference samples from conventionally prepared (AR) 316L.

Two principal orientations of printed blocks (**TD** and **BD** samples) were used and compared to conventional samples (**AR**) to assess a possible effect of SLM 316L steel texture on erosion resistance. Their surfaces were exposed to water jet impingement using the PWJ technique as follows:

- In the case of **TD** samples, PWJ was applied on the side surface, and the orientation between the build direction and jet direction was perpendicular (**Figure 5 c**)
- In the case of **BD** samples, PWJ was applied on the top surface, and the orientation between the build direction and jet direction was parallel (**Figure 5 d**)
- PWJ treatment was applied on the top/rolled surface of **AR** samples of conventional steel after the surface preparation (**Figure 5 e**)

To maintain the same conditions in terms of surface topography and **roughness**, the exposed surfaces of all samples before PWJ treatment were polished mechanically with SiC papers up to 4000 grit size and finalized by electrochemical polishing using a solution consisting of 500 ml ethanol, 7.5 ml nitric acid, and 25 ml perchloric acid under voltage 60 V (current < 5A) for 2 min at temperature $-15\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. It led to the linear roughness parameter $R_a = 0.4\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ evaluated according to the standard (ISO 25178-2) [31] for sample surfaces of all microstructural states. Application of PWJ with variable exposure time and technological conditions resulted in different surface roughening and erosion stages (incubation, accumulation, and attenuation).

3. Results

3.1. Erosion

Surface damage induced by applying PWJ under increasing exposure time was observed using SEM in the whole range of exposure times. Two of the most extreme times, **1 s** and **10 s** were selected from the wide range of applied exposure times to compare results and highlight the differences in the response of materials to PWJ treatment.

Figure 6 SEM overview of PWJ exposed areas treated at boundary exposure times 1 s and 10 s for all material states of 316L steel.

Figure 6 shows the overview of the impinged areas for all material states (conventional **AR** compared to SLMed in **TD** and **BD** orientation and **AB**, **SR**, and **SA** heat-treated states). The minimum exposure of 1 s caused mild erosion or only surface roughening, regardless of the material state. The visibility of the roughening is very sensitive to brightness and contrast conditions. The presence of randomly distributed tiny pits is observable in the case of the SLMed **BD** sample in the **SA** state. The effect of the interaction of the pits with water impingement is visible in the form of upheaved material on the pit edges. The maximum applied exposure of 10 s led to significant material removal in all cases, where the erosion kerf with variable depth is partially surrounded by upheaved material.

Generally, all the erosion kerfs exhibit directionality, where part of the eroded area edge shows the upheaved material termed as the pile-up, behind which material damage is hardly observable. It indicates that pile-up, created as a result of a lateral jet, partially shields the rest of the surface from the erosive action of water. Occasionally, features resembling chimney vents are observed behind the

upheaved material, evidencing the presence of subsurface tunneling. These features were described in [32] or [11] as openings or exits of transient cavities. On the opposite side of the erosion crater, the transition is more gradual from the area with material volume removal to the undamaged area. In the direction from the center of the crater to the undamaged surface, different erosion areas, such as the initial material damage, material roughening, plastic deformation, and unaffected material, are observable. This uneven distribution of eroded damage has been described in a study [33], where areas, termed segments, are divided into: localized damage segment, transitional segment, and low damage segment, based on their relative total height of primary profile (Pt) or kernel average misorientation. These topography features are best observed on erosion craters at higher exposure times. **Figure 7** shows a micrograph of a selected example of erosion kerf created by **10 s** exposure to PWJ with overlay of highlighted characteristic segments. The dominant part is an eroded area, termed the localized damage segment, characterized by significant material volume removal with evenly distributed deep erosion valleys. The second part, which is termed the transitional segment [33], shows a transition from initial erosion damage denoted by cracks, surface cavities on surface steps, or emergent grain boundaries. Through a roughened area signified by several emergent grain boundaries and surface steps, but with a diminishing amount of material damage. The low damage segment shows a diminishing number of surface steps and emergent grain boundaries, and spans from the transitional segment to the adjacent unaffected material.

Figure 7 An example of an erosion crater for exposure to PWJ for 10 s, indicating several areas with different material damage/removal characteristics.

A thorough analysis of characteristic details of erosion damage after exposure to PWJ for **1 s** and **10 s** captured by SEM in smaller (P. mag 500x) and higher (P. mag 5000x) magnifications, is presented in the following figures. **Figure 8** shows results for the conventional as-received state of material (**AR**).

Figure 9 and **Figure 10** describe characteristic features of erosion obtained on SLMed samples with two orientations between building direction and the direction of PWJ treatment (**TD** and **BD** samples) in three material states concerning the heat treatment (**AB**, **SR**, and **SA**).

Erosion details observed on the conventional **AR** material are displayed in **Figure 8**. The action of **1 s** of repetitive droplet impingement results in significant roughening, where closer observation reveals two features. The first is the appearance of arrays of parallel surface steps inside the grains. Similar surface steps were observed, described, and explained in [16]. The second feature is an observable protrusion on the grain boundaries, which leads to microscopic damage. The surface steps are linked to crystallographic orientation. The areas of surface steps inside the grains seem to be less prominent than the surface steps developed at the grain boundaries. Exposure to PWJ for **10 s** results in the micro-tunneling effect at the edge of the eroded crater. Water, due to lateral outflow, enters the cavity inside the erosion crater (cavity entrance) and creates a tunnel by deepening the cavity. These cavities can be divided into blind cavities, i.e., tunnels without exit, and transient cavities, i.e., with an exit [11]. The high magnification detail of **10 s** exposure shows an area below the pile-up region inside the crater exhibiting signs of damage propagation.

Figure 8 Surface of conventional AISI 316L in the as-received state subjected to erosion time 1 s and 10 s documented by SEM.

The erosion effect of the PWJ action on the surface of the **TD** sample is shown in **Figure 9** for three material states (**AB**, **SR**, and **SA**). The **AB** state shows surface steps created at the grain boundaries as well as arrays of surface steps within the steps. The detail shows arrays of surface steps after **1 s** exposure in adjacent grains. (see **Figure 9**, **AB** state, mag 5000x). The damage progression from the crater (left) to the adjacent material (right) is apparent in the case of **10 s** exposure. The detail shows the formation of microscopic cavities following the pattern of surface steps, a sign of the beginning of material removal in the observed area.

The **SR** state exhibits, after **1 s** exposure, the formation of a slightly higher number of surface steps inside the grains and more prominent surface steps at grain boundaries. The most prominent surface step at the grain boundary is captured in the figure (see **Figure 9**, **SR** state, mag 500x) shows an already initiated crack. The detailed view shows the adjacent area with a dense array of parallel surface steps perpendicular to a crack. The image of **10 s** exposure is focused on the edge of the erosion crater. Open and semi-closed cavities interfering with the pile-up are observed. The detail of the selected cavity shows a crack connecting the cavity entrance to the cavity exit. It allows us to assume the direction of the tunneling effect. The vicinity of the cavity exit shows a high number of surface steps, indicating the deformation direction. The lateral outflow forces water to impinge on the entrance to the cavity inside the erosion crater (cavity entrance) and creates a tunnel by deepening the cavity. Both the blind and transient cavities can be visible in **Figure 9**. These transient cavities are one of the possibilities for lateral outflow to move through the pile-up. The material flow forced by lateral outflow and cavities interaction is also an explanation of the upheaved material on the outside of the pile-up.

The **SA** state treated by PWJ for **1 s** shows surface steps at grain boundaries and surface steps inside grains. The detail shows the complex arrays of surface steps. The possible mechanism of this surface step array creation may be the interaction of surface steps with the annealing twin. This mechanism is supported by the abrupt disappearance of surface steps at the top edge of the figure. Another detail shows the change of orientation of surface steps, which can be attributed to either a twin or a grain boundary. Exposure to PWJ for **10 s** exhibits numerous cavities of varying sizes and, in some cases, cracks interconnecting the cavities at the bottom of the erosion crater.

Figure 9 SLMed 316L steel TD samples in **AB**, **SR**, and **SA** state, subjected to PWJ exposure for 1 s and 10 s documented by SEM.

Selected erosion patterns of the **BD** sample in all material states (**AB**, **SR**, and **SA**) are documented in **Figure 10** for PWJ exposure of **1 s** and **10 s**. The **AB** state after **1 s** exposure shows surface steps and exposed grain boundaries. The surface steps are considerably more prominent (contrary to **TD** samples in **Figure 9**), and some already show signs of initiation of erosion damage. The micrograph of the surface after **10 s** exposure focuses on the bottom of the erosion crater. The detail shows numerous cavities of various sizes surrounded by secondary cracks spreading in a radial direction from the main cavity. The adjacent areas appear to be heavily smoothed, probably caused by the action of lateral flow.

The **SR** state exposed to **1 s** PWJ shows damage mechanisms comparable to those of the **AB** state. The detailed view reveals the grain with a dense array of surface steps. **10 s** exposure exhibits a heavily roughened area adjacent to the main erosion crater. The damage seems to be randomly distributed with several surface cavities. A trio of surface cavities in a similar direction and with characteristic curved trajectories is recognizable. The area above these cavities shows signs of local upheaval of the material. The orientation of the elongated cavities, together with upheaved material like pile-up and smooth surrounding of the cavities, suggests that lateral outflow jetting significantly influenced the morphology of this area.

The **SA** state of the **BD** sample treated by **1 s** exposure to PWJ shows damage features in the form of surface steps (analogously to the **TD** sample in the **SA** state in **Figure 9**). It is especially apparent from the detailed view where an array of surface steps abruptly ends at a single boundary. After **10 s** of PWJ exposure, a significant pile-up surrounding the subsection protruded from the crater, as is shown in the edge region. A dashed line indicates the probable direction of the primary lateral flow orientation. The arrows show the branching of pathways probably created in the pile-up, as escape points due to lateral outflow acting. The detail shows a crack propagating through the pile-up. The condition created behind the pile-up caused the formation of an interlaced network of surface steps.

Figure 10 SLMed 316L steel BD sample in as-built (AB), stress relieved (SR), and solution annealed (SA) state subjected to erosion times 1 s and 10 s documented by SEM.

3.2. Surface topography

The surface topography created by incrementing PWJ exposure was evaluated using an InfiniteFocus G5 optical system. **Figure 11** shows a comparison of results in the form of three-dimensional views of the surface damage induced by PWJ on each tested material condition. Within scanned areas of identical size of $3 \times 3 \text{ mm}^2$, the differences in surface topography displayed at the same height scale, ranging from $-450 \mu\text{m}$ to $+250 \mu\text{m}$, are apparent. The extent of height range in all 3D micrographs was selected to render fully the whole depth of craters created by the longest exposure.

Two levels of exposures, i.e., **1 s** and **10 s**, presented in the previous results of SEM observation were supplemented in **Figure 11** by **5 s** exposure. The shortest exposure time of **1 s** resulted in a flat and only slightly roughened surface topography for all the material states, i.e., in the incubation period, without erosion. The 3D picture shown in **Figure 11** for **1 s**, and a conventional **AR** sample can interpret topography results for all other material states, confirming no material removal. The medium exposure time of **5 s** represents the acceleration stage of erosion. Topography results presented in **Figure 11** for **5 s** show the signs of erosion marks. The most significant difference in erosion resistance is observable in the case of the **SA** state, where the **TD** sample exhibits a smaller erosion mark, i.e., the higher erosion

resistance to PWJ in comparison with the **BD** sample or conventional **AR** sample. The comparison between **TD** samples under variable heat treatments provides higher erosion resistance for the **AB** state. The surfaces exposed to PWJ for **10 s** are typical with erosion marks with a fully developed crescent shape. Qualitative assessment of results indicates the deepest and the widest erosion in the case of the conventional **AR** state, followed by SLMed **BD** samples, and finally **TD** samples. The effect of heat treatment is most observable from a comparison of **AB** and **SA** states of **TD** samples (see the color map), confirming slightly higher resistance to water jet impingement for **AB** state.

AR samples. SLMed samples exhibited approximately the same response to PWJ treatment regardless of the heat treatment state. Nevertheless, printing orientation was observed to have a certain effect on erosion behavior. The erosion depth for **AR** samples increased from $115 \pm 41 \mu\text{m}$ to $445 \pm 99 \mu\text{m}$ with increasing time exposure from **4 s** to **9 s**. A slight decrease in erosion depth to $426 \pm 35 \mu\text{m}$ was detected for an exposure time of **10 s**. Analogically, a similar situation is in the case of eroded volume, where the value increased from $0.012 \pm 0.01 \text{ mm}^3$ to $0.245 \pm 0.02 \text{ mm}^3$ for time exposure from **4** to **9 s**, with a slight decrease to $0.241 \pm 0.03 \text{ mm}^3$ at **10 s**.

Preprint

Figure 12 Erosion evolution characterized by a), c), e) maximum depth, and b), d), f) removed material volume plotted as a function of PWJ exposure time for all variants of 316L steel manufactured conventionally and additively by SLM.

Certain differences in the erosion behavior of SLMed variants with respect to heat treatment and printing orientation where the comparison is graphically expressed in **Figure 12a, b** for samples

without heat treatment (**AB**), **Figure 12c, d** for samples after **SR** heat treatment, and **Figure 12e, f** for samples after **SA** heat treatment. In each plot, the erosion data for **TD** and **BD** samples are compared.

The maximum depth of erosion exhibited an increasing trend. **AB** state reached values from $160 \pm 69 \mu\text{m}$ to $381 \pm 93 \mu\text{m}$ for the **TD** sample and from $127 \pm 76 \mu\text{m}$ to $413 \pm 84 \mu\text{m}$ for the **BD** sample. The heat treatment of samples (**SR** and **SA**) showed erosion depth trends similar to those of the **AB** sample. The erosion depth increased from $158 \pm 78 \mu\text{m}$ to $328 \pm 42 \mu\text{m}$ for the **TD** sample in **SR** state, from $82 \pm 33 \mu\text{m}$ to $359 \pm 20 \mu\text{m}$ for the **TD** sample in **SA** state, from $120 \pm 34 \mu\text{m}$ to $356 \pm 33 \mu\text{m}$ for the **BD** sample in **SR** state, and from $161 \pm 69 \mu\text{m}$ to $394 \pm 53 \mu\text{m}$ for the **BD** sample in **SA** state.

The situation with eroded volume is similar to erosion depth. The **AB** state exhibits an increase in values from $0.017 \pm 0.006 \text{ mm}^3$ to $0.156 \pm 0.02 \text{ mm}^3$ for the **TD** sample and from $0.016 \pm 0.02 \text{ mm}^3$ to $0.15 \pm 0.01 \text{ mm}^3$ for the **BD** sample. The volume measurements for the **SR** and **SA** states don't differ much, so the effect of heat treatment is negligible. Nevertheless, printing orientation played a certain role when **BD** samples reached higher values of eroded volume compared to **TD** samples. The eroded volume for the **SR** state increases from $0.013 \pm 0.007 \text{ mm}^3$ to $0.118 \pm 0.01 \text{ mm}^3$ for the **TD** sample and from $0.01 \pm 0.005 \text{ mm}^3$ to $0.13 \pm 0.01 \text{ mm}^3$ for the **BD** sample. The **SA** state increases from $0.005 \pm 0.003 \text{ mm}^3$ to $0.145 \pm 0.022 \text{ mm}^3$ for the **TD** sample and from $0.026 \pm 0.02 \text{ mm}^3$ to $0.185 \pm 0.07 \text{ mm}^3$ for the **BD** sample. The **BD** sample in **SR** state shows better erosion resistance in terms of both maximal depth and removed volume than the **AB** and **SA** samples for longer exposure times within the tested exposure interval.

4. Discussion

PWJ treatment of additively manufactured metals is a novel research area. In this work, the erosion effects of PWJ treatment on 316L stainless steel produced conventionally and using SLM technology were at the center of interest. A significant aspect of this research is the consideration of microstructural texture affected by SLM, heat treatment, and the relation between the direction of applied PWJ and building direction from the SLM process. This approach allows for a comprehensive understanding of how orientation and manufacturing methods affect the material's resistance to erosion.

Techniques of additive manufacturing suffer from the negative effects of printing defects on final material properties. The presence of keyholes is usually observed in the near-surface layer, mainly close to the interface between the contour and inner regions [34]. Prior to water jetting, the sample surface was polished, i.e., the keyholes in the close subsurface (especially in the case of vertically printed samples – see **Figure 5c**) can occasionally emerge (see **Figure 9, AB** state, mag 5000x). The density of the samples evaluated by Archimedes method for the SLM material variant was very high, indicating that the presence of such a defect was sporadic and thus the possibility that PWJ would impinge on this specific locality was extremely low. In this case, no substantial effect of printing defects on observed erosion behavior during PWJ treatment is expected.

Samples prepared by SLM generally exhibit the presence of residual stresses [25]. This situation is relevant to the **AB** state possessing a typical cellular dislocation substructure. The level of residual stress may be affected by pertinent post-heat treatment. **SR** treatment significantly decreases internal stress without a significant change in internal microstructure, i.e., keeping partially the dislocation cell structure and fully the grain structure. In the case of the **SA** state, recrystallization results in a state with both significant change of microstructure (i.e., loss of original cell structure) and complete removal of internal stresses. According to the hypothesis, the annealing resulted in a decrease in dislocation density, which allows for higher plastic deformation. Nevertheless, differences in measured

values and presented plots on surface erosion damage were not observed to depend on post-heat treatment, i.e., no significant differences in erosion resistance of SLMed samples with and without post-heat treatment could be clearly recognized within experimental data for a given specimen printing orientation (**TD**, **BD**). The changes in the mechanical properties of SLMed 316L steel related to post-heat treatment conditions did not significantly affect the erosion behavior.

SEM observation of erosion craters revealed the presence of surface steps inside grains in the deformed area. In the literature, the formation of surface steps by PWJ treatment was reported [30], related to slip marks and twins. The effect of heat treatment on the creation of surface asperities was not confirmed; nevertheless, in the case of different orientations, i.e., **TD** and **BD** samples, it seems that higher steps were created by applying PWJ in the case of **BD** samples. It could be related to the lower yield strength of **BD** samples due to the preferred orientation of elongated grains growing through melt pools in the build direction.

The incubation period of PWJ is defined as the phase during which plastic deformation and internal stress accumulate beneath the surface before notable material loss occurs. In this phase, the compendious impact energy does not exceed the material's ultimate strength; nevertheless, it overcomes the local yield strength, leading to the deformation of the internal microstructure of the samples. This phenomenon, called peening, enhances the mechanical properties of the sample, as observed by several studies on air [35], [36], or in submerged conditions [37], thus demonstrating the viable utilization of the PWJ technique for surface treatment for specific applications. All material states under investigation showed a particular incubation stage for short exposure times. Conventionally produced **AR** material exhibited a shorter incubation stage than SLMed variants of material, i.e., microstructure introduced into the material during SLM technology was more erosion resistant. It can be related to significantly higher dislocation density and difficult glide of dislocations of SLMed material variants.

Experimental results obtained on the length of the incubation stage, erosion depth, and eroded volume are unique. When erosion starts, an increasing trend in erosion depth/volume is observed. In the case of the conventional **AR** material state, saturation or a slight decrease in erosion capability was observed for the highest exposure time. According to Haller et al. [8], it can be explained as a possible indication of the start of the deceleration stage for applied PWJ parameters when the erosion rate declines. This effect can be explained by the accumulation of water at the bottom of the erosion crater. A stagnant water layer (which is thicker in the case of less erosion-resistant conventional **AR** material, contrary to the SLMed variants) occurring in the erosion pit prevents the subsequent water clusters from interacting effectively with the material surface, and the re-exposure of the bottom of the crater to the erosive action of the water jet is not possible. This observation aligns with other studies related to PWJ erosion, where a longer exposure time beyond a limit decreases the erosion magnitude [8], [38].

Quantitative analysis of the eroded depth and volume showed differences between the erosion resistance of **TD** and **BD** variants of SLMed samples. The **BD** samples show lower erosion resistance achieved for the same hydraulic conditions compared to the **TD** samples. It is related to the building direction and direction of PWJ treatment, as described earlier and schematically expressed in **Figure 13** and **Figure 14**.

Figure 13 Relation between erosion response and orientation of additively manufactured 316 L steel samples.

Figure 14 Relation between the orientation of the sample, the direction of acting PWJ, and texture represented by IPF in Z direction for a) BD, and b) TD SLMed samples of 316L steel.

The lower erosion resistance of **BD** samples (compared to the **TD** samples) can be attributed to the morphology of the grains created by SLM technology (i.e., texture based on grain shape, see **Figure 13**) and to the preferred crystallographic orientation of grains (see **Figure 14**).

The first aspect, i.e., the grain shape, reflects elongated grains due to the epitaxial growth through melt pools [39]. The horizontal and vertical builds show different effective grain sizes depending on the loading axis [40]. As depicted in **Figure 13**, in the case of **BD** samples, the PWJ acts in a compressive manner in a direction that is parallel with the longer axis of grains. Therefore, the material behaves as softer, and erosion is higher. In the case of **TD** samples, the loading axis, i.e., the direction of PWJ, is perpendicular to the build direction and grain axis. In this case, the effective grain size is assumed to be smaller, allowing dislocation movement along the shorter distance. When dislocation slips require higher stress, the material exhibits higher resistance to plastic deformation. It also corresponds to higher resistance to erosion wear of **TD** samples.

The preferred crystallographic orientation of elongated epitaxial grains is the second important aspect of the different response of **TD** and **BD** samples to PWJ treatment. The hardness of 316L stainless steel depends on the crystallographic orientation of grains [41]. In the present case, when the PWJ treatment is applied to the top surface of the **BD** samples, the texture in the Z direction plays an important role in erosion resistance. As apparent from **Figure 14a**, a moderate $\langle 101 \rangle$ texture is clearly present in **BD** samples. The value of MUD (multiple of uniform density) is 2. According to the color map, the grains with $\langle 101 \rangle$ direction (green) are due to their orientation to the loading axis, considered

as soft [41]. **BD** samples, therefore, exhibit lower erosion resistance. Contrary to this specimen orientation, in the case of **TD** samples, the PWJ treatment is applied on the side surface with respect to the SLM building process. The texture in the Z direction is again very important since it corresponds to the direction of PWJ impingement. As is apparent from **Figure 14b**, the **TD** samples exhibit almost no texture (MUD value of 1 indicates randomly oriented grains); nevertheless, a slight preponderance of <001> texture component may be recognized. Grains oriented in direction <001> (red according to the color map) are considered as hard [41]. It contributes to the higher erosion resistance of **TD** samples from a crystallographic point of view. Finally, it should be pointed out that the above considerations on the grain-orientation-dependent hardness for SLM 316L steel in **AB** and **SA** states are also supported by the results of Vickers hardness HV1 measurements listed in **Table 3**.

5. Conclusions

The surface of 316L steel samples fabricated conventionally and additively using SLM was treated by a pulsating water jet. PWJ technology applied with increasing jet exposition induced different levels of surface roughening and erosion. Changes in the microstructure of SLM material due to the different post-heat treatments were documented, and the effect of repetitive action of water droplets on the surface of SLM 316L steel in three different microstructural states was compared with the response of conventionally produced counterparts. The most important findings can be summarized as follows:

- The mechanical properties and microstructure of SLM 316L steel in various material states are substantially different compared to 316L manufactured conventionally. The higher resistance to water jet impingement was observed in the case of SLMed variants.
- In the case of SLM material variants, the crucial factors determining the resistance to erosion induced by PWJ are the anisotropic properties linked to the SLM building direction.
- The higher erosion resistance of SLM 316L steel can be ascribed to lower effective grain size, higher dislocation density, and the fact that the majority of grains have optimal crystallographic orientation.
- Grains with softer <101> crystallographic orientation allow more active slip planes to be involved, and therefore, they exhibit higher plastic deformation. Thus, it can shorten the incubation period and increase the extent of erosion.
- Samples submitted to the stress relief post-heat treatment exhibited the best resistance to water jet impingement, which indicated this procedure could lead to an optimum microstructural state of SLM 316L steel with the highest erosion resistance.

The considerable improvement in erosion resistance of the SLMed samples over the conventional samples confirms the hypothesis that structural parts that are exposed to frequent water droplets can be replaced with additively manufactured counterparts to reduce erosion wear and increase the service lifetime of the devices working under hydrodynamic erosive forces.

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Data availability

Data will be available following publication of this article at [10.5281/zenodo.14966093](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14966093)

References

- [1] Fujisawa K. On erosion transition from the incubation stage to the accumulation stage in liquid impingement erosion. *Wear* 2023;528–529. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wear.2023.204952>.
- [2] Ahmad M, Schatz M, Casey M V. An empirical approach to predict droplet impact erosion in low-pressure stages of steam turbines. *Wear* 2018;402–403:57–63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wear.2018.02.004>.
- [3] Hancox NL, Brunton JH. The Erosion of Solids by the Repeated Impact of Liquid Drops. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A* 1966.
- [4] Haller KK, Poulikakos D, Ventikos Y, Monkewitz P. Shock wave formation in droplet impact on a rigid surface: Lateral liquid motion and multiple wave structure in the contact line region. *J Fluid Mech* 2003. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022112003005093>.
- [5] Fujisawa K. Simulation of lateral jet formation in high-speed liquid droplet impingement and its impact on crater side wall. *Ann Nucl Energy* 2022;175. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2022.109202>.
- [6] Adler WF. The mechanics of liquid impact. *Academic Press, Treatise on Materials Science and Technology*, 1979;16:127–83.
- [7] Slot H, Matthews D, Schipper D, van der Heide E. Fatigue-based model for the droplet impingement erosion incubation period of metallic surfaces. *Fatigue Fract Eng Mater Struct* 2021;44:199–211. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ffe.13352>.
- [8] Gujba AK, Hackel L, Kevorkov D, Medraj M. Water droplet erosion behaviour of Ti-6Al-4V and mechanisms of material damage at the early and advanced stages. *Wear* 2016;358–359. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wear.2016.04.008>.
- [9] Lehocká D, Klichová D, Foldyna J, Hloch S, Hvizdoš P, Fides M, et al. Comparison of the influence of acoustically enhanced pulsating water jet on selected surface integrity characteristics of CW004A copper and CW614N brass. *Measurement (Lond)* 2017;110. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measurement.2017.07.005>.
- [10] Hloch S, Adamčík P, Nag A, Srivastava M, Čuha D, Müller M, et al. Hydrodynamic ductile erosion of aluminium by a pulsed water jet moving in an inclined trajectory. *Wear* 2019;428–429. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wear.2019.03.015>.

- [11] Hloch S, Souček K, Svobodová J, Hromasová M, Müller M. Subsurface microtunneling in ductile material caused by multiple droplet impingement at subsonic speeds. *Wear* 2022;490–491. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wear.2021.204176>.
- [12] Field JE. ELSI conference: Invited lecture liquid impact: Theory, experiment, applications. *Wear*, vol. 233–235, 1999, p. 1–12. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0043-1648\(99\)00189-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0043-1648(99)00189-1).
- [13] Foldyna J, Sitek L, Švehla B, Švehla S. Utilization of ultrasound to enhance high-speed water jet effects. *Ultrason Sonochem* 2004;11:131–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ultsonch.2004.01.008>.
- [14] Hloch S, Poloprudský J, Šiška F, Babinský T, Nag A, Chlupová A, et al. Erosion development in AISI 316L stainless steel under pulsating water jet treatment. *Engineering Science and Technology, an International Journal* 2024;50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jestch.2024.101630>.
- [15] Chlupová A, Hloch S, Nag A, Šulák I, Kruml T. Effect of pulsating water jet processing on erosion grooves and microstructure in the subsurface layer of 25CrMo4 (EA4T) steel. *Wear* 2023;524–525:204774. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wear.2023.204774>.
- [16] Poloprudský J, Gamanov S, Chlupová A, Klichová D, Nag A, Stolárik G, et al. Water droplet erosion assessment in the initial stages on AISI 316 L using kernel average misorientation. *Tribol Int* 2024;191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.triboint.2023.109165>.
- [17] Sun Z, Tan X, Tor SB, Yeong WY. Selective laser melting of stainless steel 316L with low porosity and high build rates. *Mater Des* 2016;104:197–204. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2016.05.035>.
- [18] Röttger A, Boes J, Theisen W, Thiele M, Esen C, Edelmann A, et al. Microstructure and mechanical properties of 316L austenitic stainless steel processed by different SLM devices. *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology* 2020;108:769–83. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00170-020-05371-1>.
- [19] de Souza Silva EMF, da Fonseca GS, Ferreira EA. Microstructural and selective dissolution analysis of 316L austenitic stainless steel. *Journal of Materials Research and Technology* 2021;15:4317–29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmrt.2021.10.009>.
- [20] Mohyla P, Hajnys J, Sternadelová K, Krejčí L, Pagáč M, Konečná K, et al. Analysis of welded joint properties on an AISI316L stainless steel tube manufactured by SLM technology. *Materials* 2020;13:1–14. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma13194362>.
- [21] Voisin T, Forien J-B, Perron A, Aubry S, Bertin N, Samanta A, et al. New insights on cellular structures strengthening mechanisms and thermal stability of an austenitic stainless steel fabricated by laser powder-bed-fusion. *Acta Mater* 2021;203. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2020.11.018>.
- [22] Saeidi K, Kvetková L, Lofaj F, Shen Z. Austenitic stainless steel strengthened by the in situ formation of oxide nanoinclusions. *RSC Adv* 2015;5:20747–50. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c4ra16721j>.
- [23] Gor M, Soni H, Singh Rajput G, Sahlot P. Experimental investigation of mechanical properties for wrought and selective laser melting additively manufactured SS316L and MS300. *Mater Today Proc*, vol. 62, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2022.03.511>.
- [24] Yang Y, Zhu Y, Khonsari MM, Yang H. Wear anisotropy of selective laser melted 316L stainless steel. *Wear* 2019;428–429:376–86. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wear.2019.04.001>.

- [25] Hajnys J, Pagáč M, Měsíček J, Petru J, Król M. Influence of scanning strategy parameters on residual stress in the SLM process according to the bridge curvature method for AISI 316L stainless steel. *Materials* 2020;13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma13071659>.
- [26] Cegan T, Pagac M, Jurica J, Skotnicova K, Hajnys J, Horsak L, et al. Effect of hot isostatic pressing on porosity and mechanical properties of 316 L stainless steel prepared by the selective laser melting method. *Materials* 2020;13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma13194377>.
- [27] Laleh M, Sadeghi E, Revilla RI, Chao Q, Haghdadi N, Hughes AE, et al. Heat treatment for metal additive manufacturing. *Prog Mater Sci* 2023;133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmatsci.2022.101051>.
- [28] Godec M, Zaefferer S, Podgornik B, Šinko M, Tchernychova E. Quantitative multiscale correlative microstructure analysis of additive manufacturing of stainless steel 316L processed by selective laser melting. *Mater Charact* 2020;160. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matchar.2019.110074>.
- [29] Nag A, Stolárik G, Svehla B, Hloch S. Effect of Water Flow Rate on Operating Frequency and Power During Acoustic Chamber Tuning. *Advances in Manufacturing Engineering and Materials II: Proceedings of the International Conference on Manufacturing Engineering and Materials (ICMEM 2020)*, 21–25 June, 2021, Nový Smokovec, Slovakia, Springer; 2021, p. 142–54.
- [30] Hloch S, Srivastava M, Nag A, Müller M, Hromasová M, Svobodová J, et al. Effect of pressure of pulsating water jet moving along stair trajectory on erosion depth, surface morphology and microhardness. *Wear* 2020;452–453. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wear.2020.203278>.
- [31] ISO 25178-2: Geometrical Product Specifications (GPS)--Surface Texture: Areal--Part 2: Terms, Definitions and Surface Texture Parameters. IOF Standardization - International Organization for Standardization 2012.
- [32] Nag A, Hloch S, Čuha D, Dixit AR, Tozan H, Petrů J, et al. Acoustic chamber length performance analysis in ultrasonic pulsating water jet erosion of ductile material. *J Manuf Process* 2019;47:347–56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmapro.2019.10.008>.
- [33] Poloprudský J, Chlupová A, Gamanov Š, Klichová D, Stolárik G, Nag A, et al. A kernel average misorientation evaluation of surface alterations caused by angled droplet impingements. *Engineering Science and Technology, an International Journal* 2025;69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jestch.2025.102126>.
- [34] Rivolta B, Gerosa R, Panzeri D. Selective laser melted 316L stainless steel: Influence of surface and inner defects on fatigue behavior. *Int J Fatigue* 2023;172. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2023.107664>.
- [35] Srivastava M, Hloch S, Gubelj N, Milkovic M, Chattopadhyaya S, Klich J. Surface integrity and residual stress analysis of pulsed water jet peened stainless steel surfaces. *Measurement (Lond)* 2019;143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measurement.2019.04.082>.
- [36] Siahpour P, Amegadzie MY, Moreau ED, Kalliecharan D, Monchesky TL, Tieu A, et al. Surface characteristics and residual stress generation in Ti-6Al-4 V following ultrasonic pulsed water jet peening. *Surf Coat Technol* 2022;445. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surfcoat.2022.128691>.

- [37] Hloch S, Svobodová J, Srivastava AK, Srivastava M, Poloprudský J, Nag A. Submerged pulsating water jet erosion of ductile material. *Wear* 2024;538–539. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wear.2024.205243>.
- [38] Karimi A, Martin JL. Cavitation erosion of materials. *International Metals Reviews* 1986;31. <https://doi.org/10.1179/imtr.1986.31.1.1>.
- [39] Fonda RW, Rowenhorst DJ. Crystallographic Variability in Additive Manufacturing. *IOP Conf Ser Mater Sci Eng* 2022;1249. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899x/1249/1/012007>.
- [40] Bahl S, Mishra S, Yazar KU, Kola IR, Chatterjee K, Suwas S. Non-equilibrium microstructure, crystallographic texture and morphological texture synergistically result in unusual mechanical properties of 3D printed 316L stainless steel. *Addit Manuf* 2019;28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addma.2019.04.016>.
- [41] Tekumalla S, Selvarajou B, Raman S, Gao S, Seita M. The role of the solidification structure on orientation-dependent hardness in stainless steel 316L produced by laser powder bed fusion. *Materials Science and Engineering: A* 2022;833. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msea.2021.142493>.